

Interview guide

Article “Sustainable scheduling in manufacturing: developing a research roadmap for practical implementation”

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Part 1: Background of the interviewee

1. Can you briefly describe your role and experience related to production scheduling or sustainability?
2. Have you been involved in research or case studies with companies around scheduling or sustainable production?
3. Are you familiar with sustainability assessment frameworks or optimization modeling?

Part 2: Structure of the roadmap

General

4. Looking at the overall structure of the roadmap, what are your initial thoughts?
5. Do you think this kind of structured process is useful for researchers working with real companies?
6. Does the visual design (colors, shapes, grouping) help or hinder your understanding of the process?
7. Are there any design elements you would change to make it more readable or researcher-friendly?

Columns

8. Do you think the roadmap covers all necessary stages in a sustainability-oriented scheduling research project?
9. Are the steps in logical order? Would you suggest a different sequencing or grouping?
10. Are there any stages that seem overdetailed or underdeveloped?

Rows

11. Do these five categories provide a useful and complete way to describe each step of the roadmap?
12. Do you think any categories should be added (e.g., expected outputs, academic deliverables, risks), split or expanded?
13. Are any of the existing categories unclear?
14. From a research perspective, do these categories help ensure clarity, reproducibility, and methodological transparency?

Part 3: Specific questions by step

Step 1: Sustainability baseline definition

15. Does this step make sense as the starting point for a sustainability-oriented scheduling research project?
16. Is the purpose and content of this step clear and easy to understand?
17. Do you think this step includes all the necessary elements for this stage?

18. Is this step feasible to implement in research projects involving companies?

Step 2: Analysis of the production process

19. Is the purpose and content of this step clear and easy to understand?

20. Do you think this step includes all the necessary elements for this stage?

21. Is this step feasible to implement in research projects involving companies?

Step 3: Identification of improvement areas

22. Does this step help connect the production process with sustainability goals in a meaningful way?

23. Is this kind of analysis commonly done or needed in academic research?

24. Is the purpose and content of this step clear and easy to understand?

25. Do you think this step includes all the necessary elements for this stage?

26. Is this step feasible to implement in research projects involving companies?

Step 4: Problem formulation

27. Does this step help structure a clear scheduling problem?

28. Is the purpose and content of this step clear and easy to understand?

29. Do you think this step includes all the necessary elements for this stage?

30. Is this step feasible to implement in research projects involving companies?

Step 5: Problem resolution and validation

31. Does this step appropriately reflect how researchers usually approach solving scheduling problems?

32. Is the purpose and content of this step clear and easy to understand?

33. Do you think this step includes all the necessary elements for this stage?

34. Is this step feasible to implement in research projects involving companies?

Step 6: Sustainability reassessment

35. Does this final step offer a meaningful way to evaluate the sustainability impact of scheduling decisions?

36. Do you think this reassessment process is useful or feasible for researchers in practice?

37. Is the purpose and content of this step clear and easy to understand?

38. Do you think this step includes all the necessary elements for this stage?

Provided documentation

39. Do you find it useful that the roadmap includes supporting documents at specific steps?

40. Do you think they add value to researchers applying the process?

41. Does the presence of these materials improve the clarity or usability of the roadmap as a research tool?

42. Would the availability of these documents help you (or other researchers) when conducting fieldwork, engaging with companies, or communicating findings?

43. Is there any concern that providing these kinds of tools might oversimplify or constrain how researchers approach the process?

Part 4: Iterative cycle and research contribution

Iterative cycle

44. The roadmap is cyclical so reassessment may lead to redefining the baseline. Do you think that this iterative process makes sense in the field of scheduling optimization?
45. Do you have any concerns regarding that it loops back to step 1 and maybe there are things that don't have to be done again?

Research contribution

46. Does the roadmap help structure applied research in sustainable scheduling?
47. Would it contribute to bridging theoretical modeling and practical implementation?